

Reasoning the Values of Particle Charges – 8 Theory

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T alongside the recent theoretical advancements in the subject of electrons to be a positive summation of curvature on the manifold propagating across the nuclei, it is possible to reason why electrons and protons, which are composite of arbitrary variations on the matrix tensor have the same charge. That is by using the second main equation of 8T - the coupling constants series.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard fermions and in particular quarks as arbitrary variations of a manifold which vanish into matter. The process of vanishing ensuring that no curvature is allowed. The exclusion of curvature yielding than the group suggested by Gell-Mann in the 20-th century. That is described by the main equation that describes a varying Lorentz manifold, which was invoked stationary:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Allowing it to experience arbitrary amounts of curvature, we have proven the existence of Quarks:

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

That was by discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.1), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements which differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The following procedure was presented in the thesis, given only four elements in the series and one of the pluses varied to a minus.

$$O: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0$$

There must be a way to bring it back to where it was, so the overall series can vanish, it takes another map, on the varying element to bring it back to where it was.

$$Y: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1$$

Therefore, to bring an element to itself given only two varying elements in the series we need two distinct maps, which attach a varying element to itself, by a threefold combination.

$$\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1$$

Since, we have a threefold combination that will pair the inverse in sign; so the both would vanish into zero. Thus, we can consider the total charge of the threefold combination to be an integer and its inverse:

$$\delta g_1(O)\delta g_2(Y)\delta g_1 \Leftrightarrow \delta g_2(O)\delta g_1(Y)\delta g_2$$

Similar to the group suggested by the 20-th century. We know we had two pluses and one minus in the first and since there are only three elements the charge of each must be a result of a three divisor. The sum leading to a positive integer. Then we can construct:

$$\delta g_1 = +\frac{2}{3}$$

$$\delta g_2 = -\frac{1}{3}$$

$$\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 = +1$$

$$\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 = -1$$

$$\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \Leftrightarrow \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2 \quad (1.3)$$

Will pair exactly to zero, that is in agreement with the charges of elementary quarks and in the 8T arbitrary variations of curvature on the matrix tensor. Since the electron is not a composite of any kind, he must have an integer sign charge as well, which vanish into zero within larger matter clusters by the right term of (1.34). The vanishing is done via an inverse set of electrons spinning to opposite direction ensuring $\delta g_k = 0$ as presented in equation (1.34).

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N e_i \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N (+3)_i > 0 \quad (1.33)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i > 0 \cap \sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (1.34)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^T (-3)_i + \sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i = 0; \quad T = N \quad (1.35)$$

From such a construction than it is clear that electrons must have a charge that is integer, as there are not a composite, and charge that must vanish into zero by demands of stationary Lorentz manifold.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i \rightarrow (+1) \quad (1.36)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (-3)_i = (-1) \quad (1.37)$$

Therefore, by using new theory of Variational curvature framework and the new insights regarding the electron adding up to a positive summation of curvature advancements can be made. In particular, advancements in reasoning why protons and electrons have exactly the same charge. The underlining reason is linked to stationarity demands on the metric tensor of the manifold and composite curvatures versus elementary curvatures.

References

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- [2] O. Manor. "Curvature and Probability of Arrival" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is Short Ranged" In: (2021)